

DETERMINATION OF PHYTATE CONTENTS IN CASSAVA SAMPLES CULTIVATED IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Analyses of the phytate and total phosphorus (P) compositions of fourteen different varieties of cassava grown in Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Nigeria were carried out using standard method of analyses. The samples were separated thus: tuber (head, middle and tail), leaves and stem. The results based on dry weight showed that phytate ranged from 203.8-383.4mg100g⁻¹, (head), 213.0-383.0 mg100g⁻¹ (middle), 213.0-372.8 mg100g⁻¹ (tail), 213-383.5 mg100g⁻¹ (leaves) and 213.0-355 mg100g⁻¹ (stem). The middle of the tubers had highest total P. More than half of the cassava samples had over 70% of their total P linked to phytate. The coefficient of variation in percent (CV %) of all-the samples revealed that there were no great disparity between the parameters measured. The relative high phytate value obtained in this study suggests that the bioavailability of metals in the samples should be adequately processed so that the concern posed by the metal chelation and protein – binding action of phytate would be eliminated.

KEYWORDS: Phytate, cassava parts, binding action, metal chelation, processing methods, Phytate mineral complex.

INTRODUCTION

Cassava is a staple crop in Nigeria and other West African countries where both its roots and leaves are used for man and livestock. It has been grown under a wide range of agro-ecologies throughout the country. In periods of acute shortage of the country's staple, rice, the crop has served to alleviate hunger in many households. There has been a trend increases in cassava production in the humid tropics, management practices are variable and in most systems inappropriate for the expression of the yield potentials of the improved cassava genotypes (Ene – Okro *et al* 1998).

Fresh roots of cassava contains about 30 – 35% starch, less than 1% protein, about 15mg, vitamin C and 20mg% Ca, it has the highest energy and starch content. It is high in dietary fiber, Mg, Na, vitamin B₁, B₂, ascorbic acid and citrate and low in protein, Fe, K, S and vitamin A. Peels are richer in proteins, both extract and ash than the edible portions (Ekpeyoung 1984 and Eka 1998).

Many cassava based diets has been formulated to suit different purposes, for example, cassava bread, sausage rolls, cookies, doughnuts, flakes, biscuits and chinchin (Onabolu *et al* 1998).

Phytate is one of the allelochemicals found in foods (Aletor 1993). It is nutritionally important because of the formation of complexes with magnesium, calcium and proteins (Abulude *et al* 2005a), thereby making them unavailable for man and animals (Wyatt and Triana-Tejas 1994). By competitive chelate formation phytate participates in the process of intestinal absorption of Ca, Mg and Fe ions. This formation of insoluble chelate complexes of phytate accounts for some of its extremely important properties. Further more, phytate is the most important anti-nutritional factor because more than 50% of P is present in the form of phytate in cereals, legumes, seed, sand organic soils (Oberleas 1983) serving as a phosphate deport in the body which is broken down by phytase to myo-inositol (human body contains 40g of myo-inositol).

It also plays the role of a growth factor. Myo-inositol increase the oxygen transporting capacity of hemoglobin in red blood cells, improves and regulates cellular metabolism, especially, in conditions of P deficiency in the body, stimulates hemopoiesis and bone tissue formation and also improves the tone of the nervous system. Phytate has also been shown to play a role in preventing colorectal carcinoma hypercholesterolemia and renal calculi (Marounek *et al* 2000)

Several research works have been carried out on the phytate content of cassava (Eka 1977, Oberleas 1983, Harland *et al* 1988, Marfo *et al* 1990), but there is dearth of information on the phytate contents of cassava leaves, stem and tuber (head, middle and tail). It is therefore the objectives of this work to quantify the total P and phytate distribution in fourteen different varieties of cassava grown in Akure, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample source

Fourteen cassava samples grown in the Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Nigeria (7°N, 5°101E) and harvested in August 2006 were used for this study. The rainfall was between 1100 to 15mm per annum and temperature was 24°C.

Treatments were arranged in a split plot design with three replications sample preparation. Each sample was separated into tuber, stem and leaves. Each tuber was peeled, washed, cut into chunks, oven dried at 110°C, ground with mortar and pestle, sieved (2mm wire mesh) and stored in plastic containers at room temperature.

The stem and leaves were washed, oven dried at 110 C, ground with mortar and pestle, sieved (2mm wire mesh) and stored in plastic containers prior to analysis.

ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES

Each of the samples (0.5g) was dry ashed in muffle furnace at 550°C for 3h. The ashed samples were dissolved in 2M HCL, filtered and made to volume (50cm³) with 2M HCL. Total P was determined in each solution colorimetrically using phosphovanadomolybdate method (AOAC 1990).

Phytate was determined using a combination of two methods. Extraction and precipitation of phytate were carried out, while iron in the precipitate was determined by the method of Makower (1970). Phytate P was calculated as a percentage of total P.

Quality control

To minimize the risk of adventitious contamination, all glass wares used in the analysis were acid-washed and sterile disposable non powered gloves were worn when handling samples. Three replicates of the samples were analyzed to check the reproducibility and accuracy of the analytical methods respectively. The mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation in percent were determined using an SPSS for 10.0 and are listed in Table 1

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The total P, phytate P, phytate and phytate as % of total P for all the cassava samples analyzed expressed on a dry weight basis are presented in Table 1. The total P content of samples ranged from 80 to 120mg100g⁻¹ dry weight. Also expressed on a dry weight basis, the leaves generally had higher P contents compared to the stem. Samples 99/307.3, 98/0581 and 99/2123 had the highest values (120mg100g⁻¹) of all the samples.

The phytate P content of all the samples analyzed ranged from 60 mg100g⁻¹ (94/0039) to 108mg100g⁻¹. Tuber (head and middle) and leaves had the highest phytate P followed by the tail of tuber and stems.

The phytate content of the tubers (head and middle) and leaves were markedly higher than those of tubers (tail) and stems. This was depicted by the means values of all the samples analyzed. All the groups showed marked variability in phytate content. Samples 99/3073, 98/0581, M98/0068, 92B/00061, 96/1632, 97/4763, 98/0002 and 99/2123 have the highest phytate contents (i.e less than 215 mg100g⁻¹ dry weight.). High phytate P as % of total P (i.e > 70%) were found in the samples. Most samples in the tubers (tail) had phytate P as % of total P greater than 100%. Only sample 98/2226 (stem) had less than 70%.

In general, good agreement was found between the phytate content of the cassava samples analyzed in this study and those obtained by Ferguson *et al* (1988) for East African Foods, Fagbemi *et al*, (2005) for tropical seeds, Abulude (2001) for vegetables, Hagir *et al* (2005) for Faba bean, AbdulRahaman *et al* (2005) for millet cultivars and Awada *et al* (2005) for maize, lentil and cassava (Table 2). The exceptions were for sorghum (Idris *et al* 2005) and mushrooms (Abulude 2005a). The differences recorded in our study and others could be due to the fact that phytate content varies considerably, depending upon the variety and/or cultivar, climatic conditions, irrigation conditions, type of soil, analytical methods and year during which they are grown. Such differences are not unexpected.

The total P and phytate P values recorded in this study were similar or in agreement with the concentrations found for tropical seeds and vegetables reported in the literatures. Phytate P in several seed and grains has been reported to constitute the major portion of total P. For example, phytate P represents the following percentages of the total P: a 81.0% in rice, 83.0-88.0% in corn, 60.0-80.0% wheat and 79.0% in black grain (Reddy *et al* 1982). It is then correct to conclude that our results were in agreement with the report of Reddy *et al* (1982). More than half of the cassava samples investigated had over 70% of their total P linked to phytate.

Phytate – mineral complexes are well documented (Reddy *et al* 1982, Abulude 2005b). The nutritionally important minerals such as Ca Mg, Cu, Fe³⁺, Fe²⁺ and other form complexes with phytate resulting in reduced solubility of metals. The nutritional rickets and osteomalacia in humans are related to high phytate intakes in the form of chapattis (unleavened bread), vitamin D metabolism by phytate, all these are independent of Ca absorption in the intestine.

The availability of P when present in the form of phytate depends on the species, the age of human and animal and the levels of phytase activity in the intestinal tracts of the specific species. Phytase hydrolyzes phytate into inositol and phosphates or phosphoric acid. Phytate is regarded generally as being less biologically available than the most inorganic P.

The high phytate content present in the samples analyzed may form complexes with dietary essential minerals such as Ca, Zn, Fe, Mg and makes them less biologically for absorption, it is then suggested that before consuming these samples, they could be subjected to the followings: Cooking, autoclaving, canning, germination, hydrolysis, autolysis and fermentation.

Statistical results in Table 1 showed that the coefficient of variation in percent for each sample part was low, between 8.0-31.9%. This meant that there was no great disparity between the parameters measured in the samples.

CONCLUSION

From the results it is concluded that the samples contained high quality of phosphorus and phytate contents. One problem that may hinder the utilization of minerals proteins and energy of the cassava samples is the high phytate content. This problem can be solved if the samples are subjected to different processing methods. It may be inferred that the local methods of food processing used in Nigeria can minimize the

concerns posed by metal chelation and protein-building action brought by the phytate naturally present in cassava samples under this study.

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Table 1: Total phosphorus (P), Phytate concentration (Phytate P (% of total P) of cassava tuber analyzed

Code no	Head				Middle				Tail			
	Total P (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (% of total P)	Total P (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate p (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (% of total P)	Total (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (% of total P)
1. 99/3073	120	98	347.9	81.7	110	88	312.4	80.0	99	84	298.2	84.9
2. 94/0039	80	65	203.8	81.3	74	60	213.0	81.1	74	60	213.0	81.1
3.96/0523	100	72	255.6	72.0	89	70	248.5	78.7	70	68	241.4	97.1
4.98/0581	120	100	355.0	83.3	120	92	326.6	76.1	100	92	326.6	92.0
5. M98/0068	110	98	347.9	89.1	101	98	347.9	97.0	98	98	347.9	100.0
6.30572	90	74	262.7	82.2	88	70	248.5	79.6	72	68	241.4	94.4
7. 97/4779	95	69	245.0	76.9	90	69	248.5	79.6	67	69	245.0	103.0
8. 98/2101	95	73	259.2	76.9	95	70	248.5	73.7	73	62	220.1	84.9
9. 92B/00061	102	98	347.9	96.1	101	100	355.0	99.0	92	95	337.3	103.3
10.96/1632	108	98	347.9	90.7	102	98	347.9	96.1	90	95	337.3	105.6
11. 97/4763	111	102	362.1	91.9	114	100	355.0	87.7	100	102	362.1	102.0
12. 98/0002	115	108	383.4	93.9	110	108	383.4	98.2	105	105	372.8	100.0
13. 99/2123	120	100	355.0	83.3	121	101	358.6	83.5	95	93	330.2	97.9
14. 98/2226	98	72	255.6	73.5	74	70	248.5	94.6	72	70	248.5	92.2
Minimum	80	65	203.8	72.0	74	60	213.0	76.7	67	60	213	81.1
Maximum	120	108	383.4	96.1	121	108	383.4	99.0	105	105	372.8	105.6
Mean	104.6	87.6	309.3	83.5	99.2	85.3	302.8	85.9	82.9	95.6	294.4	95.6
Standard deviation	12.3	15.5	58.3	8.0	15.1	16.2	57.5	9.2	13.9	16.0	56.8	7.7
Coffin var (%)	11.8	17.6	18.8	9.6	16.3	19.0	19.0	10.7	16.2	19.3	19.3	8.0

Table 2 : Total phosphorus (P), phytate concentration, phytate P (% of total P) of cassava leaves and stem analyzed

Code no	Leaves				Stem			
	Total P (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (% Of total P)	Total (mg100g ⁻¹)	PhytateP (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (% of total P)
1. 99/3073	100	92	326.6	92.0	100	90	319.5	92.0
2. 94/0039	72	60	213.0	85.7	82	60	213.0	73.2
3.96/0523	93	72	255.6	77.4	90	70	248.5	77.8
4.98/0581	110	93	330.2	84.6	110	93	330.2	84.6
5. M98/0068	100	92	326.6	92.0	98	91	323.1	92.9
6.30572	80	70	248.5	87.5	80	70	248.5	87.5
7. 97/4779	90	69	245.0	76.7	88	64	227.2	72.7
8. 98/2101	91	70	248.5	76.9	91	65	230.8	71.4
9. 92B/00061	100	92	326.6	92.0	98	91	323.1	92.9
10.96/1632	108	95	337.3	88.0	102	95	337.3	93.1
11. 97/4763	100	98	347.5	98.0	100	98	347.5	98.0
12. 98/0002	112	98	383.4	96.4	110	100	355.0	90.9
13. 99/2123	120	100	355.0	83.3	112	98	347.5	87.5
14. 98/2226	98	70	248.5	87.5	98	68	241.4	69.4
Minimum	72	60	213.0	76.7	82	60	213.0	71.4
Maximum	120	108	383.4	98.0	112	100	355.0	93.1
Mean	98.1	84.4	299.5	87.0	97.1	82.4	276.6	84.6
Standard deviation	12.6	15.1	53.5	6.8	10.0	15.0	88.2	9.7
Coff. var (%)	12.9	17.9	17.9	7.9	10.3	18.2	31.9	11.5

Table 3: Comparison of our results with the literature

Sample	Phosphorus (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate P (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate (mg100g ⁻¹)	Phytate (% of total P)	Country	Reference
1. African foods	-	-	219 – 1410	-	Ghana & Malawi	Ferguson <i>et al</i> (1988)
2. Tortillas	-	-	123 – 732	-	Mexico	Wyatt and Triana-tejas (1994)
3. Selected foods	-	-	0 – 1046	-	Nigeria	Adeyeye <i>et al</i> (2000)
4. Tropical seeds	41 – 78	100 – 280	360 – 990	19.2 – 57.1	Nigeria	Fagbemi <i>et al</i> (2005)
5. Vegetables	270 – 460	110 – 330	390 – 1170	40.7 – 90.9	Nigeria	Abulude (2001)
6. Mushrooms	-	0.62 – 1.39	2.22 – 4.92	-	Nigeria	Abulude (2005b)
7. Sorghum cultivars	-	-	24.1 – 265.0	-	Sudan	Idris <i>et al</i> (2005)
8. Faba bean	196.3 – 207.9	-	225.1 – 291.2	-	Sudan	Hagir <i>et al</i> (2005)
9. Pearl millet cultivars	1290.4 – 1441.1	-	245 – 1101.0	-	Sudan	Abdeha Rahaman <i>et al</i> (2005)
10. Maize and lentil	13.7 – 18.9	-	211 – 817.0	-	Sudan	Awala <i>et al</i> (2005)
11. Cassava tuber, stem, leaves	67 – 82	60 – 108	355.0 – 383.4	71.4 – 105.6	Nigeria	Our study